

APPLICATION OF EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHMS TO BUCKLING DESIGN OF FRP LAMINATED CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

Yoshio Aoki¹ and O-II Byon (Goichi Ben)²

¹ *Department of Precision Machinery Engineering, College of Science & Technology,
Nihon University, 7-24-1, Narashino-dai, Funabashi, Chiba, 274, Japan*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, College of Industrial Technology, Nihon
University, 1-2-1, Izumi-cho, Narashino, Chiba, 275, Japan*

SUMMARY: The objective of this study is the optimum buckling design of a filamentary laminated circular cylindrical shell subjected to axial compression and/or external pressure using evolutionary algorithms. The shell is composed of FRP orthotropic laminates whose principal axes coincides with the shell axes. In order to maximize the buckling load of simply supported FRP laminated cylindrical shells, the optimization of stacking sequence is studied by use of evolutionary algorithms. After various genetic parameters including the population size, the probability of mutation and the probability of crossover are tuned by the trial calculations, the evolutionary algorithms which are the combination of the global search by a genetic algorithm with local search algorithm is proposed.

KEYWORDS: stacking sequences, genetic algorithm, FRP, optimization, buckling, cylindrical shell, numerical analysis, evolutionary algorithms, orthotropic laminates

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a FRP laminated cylindrical shell have been widely used in space vehicles and pressure vessels due mainly to their potential for creating significant weight savings relative to metals. It is necessary to give full consideration to the buckling strength for the various kinds of loading such as axial compression, shear, bending and external pressure. Although, a buckling analysis of the FRP laminated cylindrical shell was carried out by many researchers, the design of an optimum satcking sequences that maximizes a buckling load calculated was a few. Hirano[1] investigated the buckling problem of six-ply, axially-compressed cylindrical shell. Starting from different initial points, his optimization procedure converged at different local maximum, and showed the multi-maximum characteristics of the objective function. Nshanian and Pappas[2] also used a nonlinear programming to determine the optimum design of laminated cylindrical shell having symmetric laminates about the mid-surface. Onoda[3] proved that the buckling load of laminated cylindrical shell was uniquely determined by 12 lamination parameters for any given material characteristics of the layer. Sun[4] developed a two-step optimization procedure combined Powell's method with a random search.

The efficiency of this procedure demonstrates for four-ply laminated cylindrical shells of various length-to-radius ratios involving three typical material systems. In the case of the nonlinear programming, it is pointed out that the optimum solution changes from the difference of the initial values. And, it is important that an optimization algorithm is able to search a global optimum solution. The genetic algorithm (GA) is recently applied to the

various optimization of composite structures [5]-[7] and is widely noticed as a new key to solution of optimizations problem.

The objective of this study is the optimum buckling design of a filamentary laminated circular cylindrical shell subjected to axial compression and/or external pressure using evolutionary algorithms. The shell is composed of FRP orthotropic laminates whose principal axes coincides with the shell axes. In order to maximize the buckling load of simply supported FRP laminated cylindrical shells, the optimization of stacking sequence is studied by use of evolutionary algorithms. After various genetic parameters including the population size, the probability of mutation and the probability of crossover are tuned by the trial calculations, the evolutionary algorithms which mean the combination of global search by a genetic algorithm with local search algorithm is proposed. In addition, EA is also applied to the multi-objective optimization that searches the maximum buckling load of FRP laminated cylindrical shell under axial compression and external pressure.

BASIC EQUATION

Let the mid-surface of the circular cylindrical shell be the reference surface, and the origin of the coordinates be located at one end of the cylindrical shell, as shown in Fig.1. The coordinates x , y and z are the axial, circumferential, and normal directions, respectively. The cylindrical shell has length L , radius R , and thickness t . Under the assumption that i th ply contains the same number of fibers in the $+\theta_i$ and $-\theta_i$ directions and they uniformly distribute through the thickness, the coupling stiffness coefficients of A_{16} , A_{26} , B_{16} , B_{26} and D_{26} in the laminates vanish. Using the linear strain displacement relations and the classical laminate constitutive relations, the shell buckling equations can be derived as follows.[8]

$$\begin{aligned}
 & A_{11}u_{,xx} + A_{12}(v_{,xy} + \frac{w_{,x}}{R}) - B_{11}w_{,xxx} - B_{12}w_{,xyy} + A_{66}v_{,xy} + A_{66}u_{,yy} - 2B_{66}w_{,xyy} = 0 \\
 & A_{66}v_{,xx} + A_{66}u_{,xy} - 2B_{66}w_{,xxy} + A_{12}u_{,xy} + A_{22}v_{,yy} + A_{22}\frac{w_{,y}}{R} - B_{12}w_{,xxy} - B_{22}w_{,yyy} = 0 \\
 & B_{11}u_{,xxx} - B_{12}v_{,xxy} + 2B_{12}\frac{w_{,xx}}{R} - D_{11}w_{,xxxx} - 2D_{12}w_{,xxyy} + 2B_{66}v_{,xxy} - A_{12}\frac{u_{,x}}{R} + 2B_{66}u_{,xyy} \\
 & - 4D_{66}w_{,xxyy} + B_{12}u_{,xyy} + B_{22}v_{,yyy} + 2B_{22}\frac{w_{,yy}}{R} - A_{22}(\frac{v_{,y}}{R} + \frac{w}{R^2}) - D_{22}w_{,yyyy} + N_x w_{,xx} + N_y w_{,yy} = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where u , v , w are displacements in the x , y and z directions, respectively. N_x , N_y are stress resultants (positive in the case of compression); A_{11} , B_{11} , D_{11}and D_{66} are components of the stiffness matrices[9] and subscript with comma indicates partial differentiation. The solutions to Eq.(1) are assumed to be

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= u_{mn} \cos(\bar{m}x) \cos(\bar{n}y) \\
 v &= v_{mn} \sin(\bar{m}x) \sin(\bar{n}y) \\
 w &= w_{mn} \sin(\bar{m}x) \cos(\bar{n}y)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where $\bar{m} = m\pi/L$, $\bar{n} = n/R$; m is the number of half-waves in the x -direction, n is the number of waves in the y -direction. These displacement functions satisfy the S-2 simply-supported

boundary conditions (that is : $w=0, M_x=0, N_x=0, v=0$). Substituting Eqn(3) into Eqn(1), the buckling loads N_x and N_y of the FRP laminated cylindrical shell under axial compression and the external pressure can be derived as a solution of an eigen value problem

$$N_x = \frac{(T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2)T_{33} + 2T_{12}T_{13}T_{23} - T_{13}^2T_{22} - T_{23}^2T_{11}}{m^2(T_{12}^2 - T_{11}T_{22})} \quad (3)$$

$$N_r = \frac{(T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2)T_{33} + 2T_{12}T_{13}T_{23} - T_{13}^2T_{22} - T_{23}^2T_{11}}{n^2(T_{12}^2 - T_{11}T_{22})}$$

where

$$T_{11} = -(A_{11}\bar{m}^2 + A_{66}\bar{n}^2)$$

$$T_{22} = -(A_{66}\bar{m}^2 + A_{22}\bar{n}^2)$$

$$T_{12} = (A_{12} + A_{66})\bar{m}\bar{n}$$

$$T_{13} = \frac{A_{12}}{R}\bar{m} + B_{11}\bar{m}^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66})\bar{m}\bar{n}^2$$

$$T_{23} = -\frac{A_{22}}{R}\bar{n} - B_{22}\bar{n}^3 - (B_{12} + 2B_{66})\bar{m}^2\bar{n}$$

$$T_{33} = -\left\{ \frac{2B_{12}}{R}\bar{m}^2 + \frac{2B_{22}}{R}\bar{n}^2 + \frac{A_{22}}{R^2} + D_{11}\bar{m}^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})\bar{m}^2\bar{n}^2 + D_{22}\bar{n}^4 \right\}$$

In the present work, the objective function may be derived as

$$f_{axial} = \text{maximize} \{ \text{minimize} [N_x(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_N, m, n)] \} \quad (5)$$

$$f_{external} = \text{maximize} \{ \text{minimize} [N_r(\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_N, m, n)] \} \quad (6)$$

with the restrictions: $m > 1, n > 0, 0 < \theta_i < 90$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, N$). That is, m and n should be selected to minimize the buckling loads θ_i is furthermore decided to obtained the maximum value of the buckling loads N_x and N_r .

OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

Evolutionary algorithm (EA) is a calculation model or algorithm imitate a process of group heredity/evolution of a creature. EA includes Genetic algorithm, Evolution Strategies and Evolutionary Programming etc. EA has four different points compared with other optimization method[10]

EA starts to searches from multi-points in a popuration, not a single point.

EA uses a fitness function, not derivatives or other auxiliary knowledge.

EA uses probabilistic transition rules, not deterministic rules.

Various individuals are appeared in the process of the crossover and mutation, then an individual having high fitness value is retained by the selection.

Design variables in this problem are considered to the ply angle and the stacking sequence of laminated cylindrical shell. It is difficult to control and manufacture a fiber orientation precisely within 3 degree in the production of FRP cylindrical shell. From this point, fiber orientation angle of each lamina θ_i converts the binary number which increase one binary every 3 or 6 degree. The example of six-ply laminates as follows.

$$[0^\circ/60^\circ/30^\circ/48^\circ/78^\circ/90^\circ] \Rightarrow [0000|1010|0101|1000|1101|1111]$$

Next, the solution space for this optimization problem be characteristic of

It is difficult to find a global optimal value since there are many local optimum values and their differences are small.

The number of lamina increase with increasing the local optimum value.

Accordingly, the suitable methods for crossover, selection and the fitness function are determined from following reasons.

Selection ; The high fitness individuals are retained to the next generation by a selection and a roulette selection, rank selection, tournament selection and elitist sampling were proposed[11]. In this plobem, the elitist sampling that always retains the best individual in the population is adopted.

Crossover ; It is exchange the section of the individual for that of another individual by a crossover and one-point crossover, multiple-point crossover and uniform crossover were proposed[12]. The central one-point crossover is adopted in this problem because it does not break a schema.

Fitness function ; The fitness function is used the difference of the buckling load and their minimum value in a population. But, since the average fitness of population goes up with the difference of fitness becomes very small, the scaled fitness function (scaling to second power or third power) is of much practical use is adopted as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{axial} &= (N_x - N_{x_min})^3 \\ F_{external} &= (N_r - N_{r_min})^2 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Next, various genetic parameters including the population size, the probability of crossover and the probability of mutation are tuned by the trial calculations. If the appropriate value of these parameters was not selected, the local optimum values are easy to be calculated. Thereupon, an appropriate value of the genetic parameter is tuned by using the following expressions are the capability of the optimal value search[13].

$$\text{Online performance} \quad P_{on}(T) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T f_E(i) \tag{8}$$

$$\text{Offline performance} \quad P_{off}(T) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T f_E^*(i) \tag{9}$$

Where T is the number of evaluation, $f_E(i)$ is the value of the objective function obtained at ith iteration and $f_E^*(i)$ is their maximum value until ith iteration.

Population size ; The effect of the population size was evaluated in the range from 10 to 150 individuals. The on-line and off-line performances are excellent at 100 individuals within the range of the probability of crossover 0.1~0.9 and the probability of mutation 0.01~0.05.

Probability of crossover ; Crossover preventes the convergence to a local optimum value. The crossover probability is evaluated within the range of 0.1~0.9. In the case of high

crossover probability for small population size(10~40) and comparatively low crossover probability for middle population size (50 or more), the on-line/off line performance is good. The crossover probability of 0.4 is regarded as an appropriate value in condition of population size of 100 individuals within the range of the mutation probability 0.01~0.05.

Probability of Mutation ; The mutation reverses the code number at an arbitrary bit of the design variable θ_i and there is possibility of find a local optimum values when the mutation probability is increased to the same as a random search (5% or more). Because the finest performance was obtained with the mutation probability 2-3% in the case of population size of 100 individuals, crossover probability 0.4~0.7, this value is regarded as an appropriate value.

From the results mentioned above, the population size of 100 individuals, the probability of crossover 0.6 and the probability of mutation 0.02 are adopted in the numerical examples of optimum stacking sequences search problems.

Figure 2 shows the change of the average fitness(the mean value of F) and the maximum fitness until 1000 generations in the case of under axial compressions. After, the average and maximum fitnesses increase until early dozens of generation, the average fitness repeats up and down due to the crossover. The maximum fitness increases rapidly as the generations by using the elitist sampling and then becomes constant at about 350 generations. Although it is seems that optimum value search is finished at this generation, the variance of the fitness of each individuals is still large (see Fig.3(b)). Therefore, the evolutionary algorithms which means the global search by the genetic algorithm and then the local search is proposed as follows:

Global search by the genetic algorithm(Exploration)

If the maximum fitness does not changed within 500th of generation continuously and the fitness over 10~20% of the population is lower than the average fitness before 500th of generations, it is decided that the global search finished. It has in remembrance all individual information of this generation and then the local search is started.

After crossover is suspended, the local search is started under the condition of the mutation probability is 5~4.5%. When the ratio of the difference between the maximum and average fitness at nth generation to the difference of both at the start of local search become to 50%, the mutation probability is changed to 4%. The mutation probability is reduced until 1% whenever this ratio reduces to 10%.

If the fitness of the individuals over 90% of population satisfies the condition of $F > F_{\max} - (F_{\max} - F_{\min})/10$, the calculation is finished.

The change of the fitnesses using by EA is shown in figure 4. The local search is started at 860th of generations because of the maximum fitness does not change after 360th of generations. The average and maximum fitness increase again, then the most of fitness are nearly equivalent to the maximum fitness is shown in Fig.3(c).

From the mentioned above, the evolutionary algorithms is used for the optimum stacking sequences search problem of FRP laminated cylindrical shells.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

FRP Laminated Cylindrical Shells Under Axial Compression

In order to show the validity of the present method, the results of the optimum stacking sequences of the simply supported Boron/Epoxy 6-ply laminated and Graphite/Epoxy 4-ply laminated cylindrical shell are compared with the results by nonlinear programming[2] and [5] in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. Material properties of the Boron/Epoxy composites are the following values, $E_L=207\text{GPa}$, $E_T=20.7\text{GPa}$, $G_{LT}=6.89\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{LT}=0.3$. The length L , radius R and thickness t of cylindrical shell are 0.3m , 0.1m and $1.524 \times 10^{-3}\text{m}$. Material properties and dimensions of Graphite/Epoxy composites are $E_L=146\text{GPa}$, $E_T=10.8\text{GPa}$, $G_{LT}=5.78\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{LT}=0.29$, $L=0.1436\text{m}$, $R=0.0825\text{m}$ and $t=5 \times 10^{-4}\text{m}$. In Table 1, nine kinds of optimum and near optimum stacking sequences and the buckling stresses are shown in the order of decreasing the buckling stress. As being pointed out by Onoda[3], our method gives many kinds of stacking sequences having almost the same buckling stress under the axial compression. Also, the numerical results of optimum stacking sequences and buckling stress are almost agreement with three kind of results in Ref.[2](# mark). The buckling stress of the six-ply optimum Boron/Epoxy shell is slightly higher than the value of four-ply shell and it is not shown in Table 1.

FRP Laminated Cylindrical Shells Under External Pressure

Table 3 and 4 show the optimum stacking sequences and buckling load of Graphite/Epoxy six-ply and four-ply laminated cylindrical shells under external pressure, respectively. In these table, all of the buckling mode are (1,7) mode and the similar optimum stacking sequences each other are obtained. It seems that the change of middle layers of laminates are not affect so much on the buckling load. A frequency of appearance in the Table 3 and 4 means the percentage of the obtained number of stacking sequences to the total number of the optimum popuratioin also shown. If the frequency of appearance is over one percent, that stacking sequence appears one time without fail in the calculation. In these tables, the numerical results of Graphite/Epoxy laminated cylindrical shell under external pressure are compared with the results by the two-step approach combined Powell's method with a random search(@ mark) and they nearly agree with each other. Then, both algorithms can be used as the method of optimal design for practical purposes. However, the evolutionary algorithms seem to less possibility of reaching the local optimum values than the nonlinear programming or the two-step approach. Furthermore, this approach has a clear advantage of computational resources over conventional nonlinear programming or the two-step approach.

Application of Multi-Objective Optimization

The evolutionary algorithm is applied to the optimum stacking sequence and the buckling stress under both loading of axial compression and external pressure. It does not consider the interaction of the axial compression load and the external pressure in this problem. The optimum solutions are obtained by utilizing the fitness function F_{multi} , that is, the magnitude of the position vector with respect to the maximum buckling load [$f_{\text{axial_max}}$ and $f_{\text{external_max}}$] as follows.

$$F_{\text{multi}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{f_{\text{axial}}}{f_{\text{axial_max}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{f_{\text{external}}}{f_{\text{external_max}}}\right)^2} \quad (10)$$

And the evolutionary algorithms added in the following procedure to the global search by GA is developed.

- 1) 50 individuals are selected by using Eq.(10) in the population.
- 2) 20~30 elite individuals which mean the individuals have high fitness are selected by each objective function are selected in the above 50 individuals and they are left to the next generation. The other individuals which are left to next generation decides by only the crossover and the mutation.
- 3) They are evaluated by only Eq.(10) in the local search.

Fig.5 shows the example of the multi-objective optimization process by EA. The initial individuals are dispersed widely in the solution plane in Fig. 5(a). After the fitness does not increase by the gloval search at 400 generations, their dispersion becomes small although each individuals are gathered to pareto plane[Fig.5(b)]. The dispersion of all individuals becomes the line in the pareto plane at 1000th generetions by the local search proress[Fig.5(c)] and validity to use the fitness finction of Eq.(10) is confirmed.

Table 5 shows the optimum stacking sequences of CF/PEEK six-ply laminated cylindrical shell under both loading of axial compression and external pressure. The material properties of CF/PEEK are $E_L=134\text{GPa}$, $E_T=12.9\text{GPa}$, $G_{LT}=6.75\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{LT}=0.298$ and the dimensions of the cylindrical shell are $L=0.3\text{m}$, $R=0.1\text{m}$ and $t=0.001\text{m}$. In Table 5, $N_x/N_{x_{\max}}$ and $N_r/N_{r_{\max}}$ are the ratio of the buckling both loading to each buckling load under pure axial compression [$N_{x_{\max}}$] and pure external pressure[$N_{r_{\max}}$], respectively. The optimum stacking sequences of CF/PEEK laminated cylindrical shell obtained by EA have many similar ones under the external pressure. It seems that the change of the fiber orientation angle of the outside layers(θ_1 , θ_2 , θ_5 and θ_6) gives effects influence largely to both of buckling load. The result of the optimum stresses under both loading are about 85% of the each maximum buckling load under single loading and the pareto optimality is satisfied. Accordingly, it consider that EA is one of useful search method for the multiobjective optimization problem.

CONCLUSION

Evolutionary algorithms (EA) is applied to the optimization of the stacking sequence in order to maximize the buckling load of FRP laminated cylindrical shell. When EA is used in the optimization pobleem, an optimum value of various parameters of EA and the reduction of the calculation time is also considered. In adition, EA is also applied to the multiobjective optimization, that is, to obtain the maximum buckling load of FRP laminated cylindrical shell under both loading of axial compression and external pressure. The following conclusions are obtained.

- 1) The numerical results of FRP laminated cylindrical shell under axial compression or external pressure obtained by the evolutionary algorithms nearly agree with the results of conventional nonlinear programming and the two-step approach.
- 2) The evolutionary algorithms seem to be less possibility of reaching the local optimum value than the nonlinear programming or the two-step approach. Furthermore, this approach has a clear advantage of computational resources over the conventional nonlinear programming or the two-step approach.

- 3) EA is also applied to the multiobjective optimization of CF/PEEK six-ply laminated cylindrical shell under both loading of axial compression and external pressure. The result of the optimum stacking sequence is $[\pm 90/\pm 24/\pm 54/\pm 54/\pm 30/\pm 90]$ laminates and the pareto optimality is satisfied. It seems that EA is one of useful search method for the multiobjective optimization problem.

REFERENCES

1. Y.Hirano, Journal of the japan society for aeronautical and space sciences, Vol.32, No.360, 1984, pp46-51
2. Y.S.Nshanian and M.Papas, AIAA Journal, Vol.21, No.3, 1983, pp430-437
3. J.Onoda, AIAA Journal , Vol.23, No.7, 1985, pp1093-1098
4. G.Sun, Composite Science and Technology, Vol.36, 1989, pp243-253
5. R.L.Riche et al , AIAA Journal , Vol.31 , No.5, 1993, pp951-956
6. Fukunaga and Sekine, Journal of the japan society for aeronautical and space sciences, Vol.42, No.485, 1994, pp371-380
7. Todoroki, Watanabe and Kobayashi, Transaction of the Japan society of mechanical engineering, Vol.60-A, No.573, 1994, pp146-151
8. J.Tasi, AIAA Journal, Vol.4 , No.6, 1966, pp1058-1062
8. Composite Material Handbook, Nikkan Kogyo Shinbun Co., 1989 chapter 1.,
9. D.B.Fogel, An Introduction to Simulated Evolutionary Optimization, IEEE Trans. On Neural Networks, Vol.5, 1994, pp.3-14
10. S.Iba, Basis of the Genetic algorithms, Ohm Co., 1994, pp93-103
11. D.E.Goldberg, Genetic Algorithms in Search Optimization & Machine Learning , Addison-Wesley Pub. Co., 1989
12. J.J.Grefenstette, Optimization of Control Parameters for Genetic Algorithms, IEEE Trans. On Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Vol.SMC-16, No.1, 1986

Fig.1 FRP laminated cylindrical shell

Fig.2 Change of the fitness with the generation(only GA)

Fig.3 Variance histogram of individuals in the population

Fig.4 Change of the fitness with the generation(EA)

Fig.5 Change of individual distribution for multi-objective optimization

Table 1 Optimum configurations for Boron/Epoxy six-ply laminated cylindrical shell under axial compression

Optimum stacking sequences	(N _x /t) [MPa]	Buckling Type
[±30/±84/±60/±6/±48/±54]	755.7	asymmetry
[±66/±18/±30/±78/±60/±30]	755.6	asymmetry
[±24/±72/±60/±12/±30/±60]	755.6	symmetry
#[±28/±65/±86/±5/±27/±63]	754.9	
[±24/±84/±42/±42/±6/±66]	755.4	asymmetry
[±66/±6/±48/±48/±84/±24]	755.4	asymmetry
[±36/±84/±0/±60/±42/±48]	755.4	asymmetry
[±54/±6/±90/±30/±48/±42]	755.4	asymmetry
#[±50/±9/±87/±7/±54/±40]	750.5	
[±36/±90/±0/±54/±48/±42]	755.2	asymmetry
[±54/±0/±90/±36/±42/±48]	755.2	asymmetry
#[±55/±2/±82/±45/±35/±48]	756.7	

Table 2 Optimum configurations for Graphite/Epoxy four-ply laminated cylindrical shell under axial compression

Optimum stacking sequences	N _x [KN/m]	Buckling mode (m,n)
[±30 / ±84 / 0 / ±60]	101.3	(1,6)
#[±32 / ±84 / 0 / ±53]	104.1	
[±60 / ±6 / ±90 / ±30]	101.3	(13,3)
#[±59 / 0 / ±90 / ±28]	101.7	
[±30 / ±84 / ±3 / ±63]	101.2	(1,6)
[±30 / ±84 / ±0 / ±57]	101.1	(13,0)
#[±33 / ±85 / 0 / ±53]	104.1	
[±30 / ±87 / ±3 / ±57]	101.1	(3,10)
#[±33 / ±89 / ±3 / ±53]	104.1	
[±30 / ±87 / ±6 / ±57]	101.1	(3,10)

Table 3 Optimum configurations for Graphite/Epoxy six-ply laminated cylindrical shell under external pressure

Optimum stacking sequences	N _r [KPa]	Frequency of appearance(%)
[±90 / ±78 / ±12 / ±18 / ±54 / ±90]	147.2	30.8
@[±90 / ±79 / ±14 / ±16 / ±54 / ±90]	147.3	
[±90 / ±78 / ±6 / ±18 / ±54 / ±90]	147.2	6.5
@[±90 / ±76 / ±5 / ±19 / ±55 / ±90]	147.3	
[±90 / ±78 / ±0 / ±18 / ±54 / ±90]	147.2	0.1
[±90 / ±78 / ±12 / ±12 / ±54 / ±90]	147.2	1.2
@[±90 / ±77 / ±14 / ±13 / ±55 / ±90]	147.3	
[±90 / ±78 / ±18 / ±12 / ±54 / ±90]	147.1	0.8
[±90 / ±78 / ±18 / ±6 / ±54 / ±90]	147.1	2.5
[±90 / ±78 / ±0 / ±24 / ±54 / ±90]	147.0	5

Table 4 Optimum configurations for Graphite/Epoxy four-ply laminated cylindrical shell under external pressure

Optimum stacking sequences	N _r [KN/m]	Frequency of appearance(%)
[±90 / ±12 / ±27 / ±90]	12.13	28.2
@[±90 / ±13 / ±27 / ±90]	12.13	
[±90 / ±15 / ±24 / ±90]	12.13	1.2
[±90 / ±9 / ±30 / ±90]	12.13	14.9
[±90 / ±18 / ±21 / ±90]	12.12	10.3
[±90 / ±6 / ±33 / ±90]	12.12	1.7

Table 5 Optimum configurations for CF/PEEK six-ply laminated cylindrical shell under axial compression and external pressure

Optimum stacking sequences	N _x /N _{x,crk} (%)	N _r /N _{r,crk} (%)	Frequency of appearance (%)
[±90/±24/±54/±54/±30/±90]	0.83	0.85	3.2
[±90/±24/±54/±54/±30/±84]	0.84	0.85	0.1
[±90/±24/±60/±48/±30/±90]	0.83	0.86	1.4
[±90/±24/±60/±42/±36/±90]	0.82	0.86	2.3
[±90/±24/±54/±48/±30/±90]	0.83	0.85	0.2
[±90/±24/±60/±48/±30/±90]	0.83	0.85	0.3
[±90/±24/±54/±54/±24/±90]	0.84	0.85	0.1
[±90/±24/±48/±60/±30/±90]	0.84	0.85	0.3
[±84/±24/±60/±54/±30/±90]	0.84	0.84	0.4
[±90/±24/±60/±42/±36/±84]	0.82	0.86	0.1